

MED-IREN: 1st PPCP Workshop

Presentation of
Outcomes and Actions
Egaleo Municipal lab 2

Presentation key points

- Overview of the MED-IREN program and its key actions.
- Transition from grey to green infrastructure with community support
- Adaptation to climate change through innovative solutions
- Policy implementation and research-driven actions
- Identifying areas for NBS implementation with citizen involvement

Key Discussion Points

- Climate indicators for Aigaleo: reduced rainfall, extreme weather events
- Increased minimum temperature and heatwaves (2025-2049 & 2045-2100)
- Vulnerability analysis: heatwave risk areas and vulnerable populations
- Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) as sustainable alternatives
- Specific solutions: tree planting, Liquid Tree, bio-bricks, Starpath

Workshop Participants

- **Public:** 4 Teachers, 7 students, 3 municipal employees (Municipal Department of Green Spaces)
- **Private:** 1 (furniture maker)
- **Civil society:** 4 parents (Parents Association), 1 citizen (Environmental NGO)
- **Partnership**

Interactive Sticker Action

- Digital mapping of the municipality
- Citizens marked NBS implementation areas with stickers : Specific solutions: tree planting(5), Liquid Tree(7), bio-bricks(3), Starpath(6)
- Encouraging public engagement in planning and urban transformation

Discussion with Participants

- Questions Raised:
 - How can these changes be integrated into local infrastructure projects?
 - Concerns about potential vandalism.
 - Can solutions be extended beyond the school area?
- Demonstration and Activity:
 - We presented a digital city map and we explained the school's selection as a demonstration site.
 - Participants placed NBS-related stickers on potential sites.
 - Suggested solutions: tree planting, bio-bricks, bio-absorbent materials, Starpath.

Parallel Awareness Actions

- School presentations on climate adaptation
- Municipality and project site publications
- Proposal for sawdust collection from municipal carpentry workshops for bio-brick production

Conclusion & Next Steps

- Citizen participation enriches urban sustainability efforts
- Further implementation of NBS solutions in selected areas
- Strengthening collaborations with schools and local stakeholders
- Expanding interactive tools for public engagement

